

A Simple Preparation of 1-Methyl-3-aryl-2-thio-2,4-(1H,3H)-quinazolidiones as Potential Antimicrobial Agents

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Quinazolin-4-ones possess wide spectrum biological activities¹. In continuation of our earlier work on the preparation of 3-aryl-2-thio-4(3H)-quinazolinones from dithiocarbamate salts and anthranilic acids², the titled compounds were synthesised and their antimicrobial activities assessed.

Results and Discussion

1-Methyl-3-aryl-2-thio-2,4-(1H,3H)-quinazolidiones (3) have been prepared by refluxing an equimolar quantities of *N*-methylantranilic acid (1) with ammonium *N*-aryldithiocarbamates (2) in absolute ethanol.

Antimicrobial activity of compounds 3a-d was evaluated by agar diffusion method³ at 500 and 1000 ppm concentrations against the bacteria *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Enterobacter* sp., *Citrobacter* sp., *Proteus vulgaris*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Vibrio cholerae* 01 classical, *Vibrio cholerae* 0139 Synonym Bengal, *Staphylococcus aureus* and at 500 ppm concentration against the fungi *Candida albicans*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Cryptococcus neoformans*, *Trichophyton violaceum* and *T. rubrum*. In the antibacterial screening, all the compounds were found inactive (zone of inhibition, 0.0–2.5 mm) against the organisms. Compounds 3a and 3b showed significant antifungal activity against *C. albicans* (11–15 mm), whereas compounds 3c and 3d exhibited moderate activity (10–12 mm) against *A. flavus* and *C. neoformans*. All the compounds were found inactive against *T. violaceum* and *T. rubrum*.

Experimental

M.ps. were determined in open capillaries on a Gallenkamp apparatus and are uncorrected. Elemental microanalyses (C, H and N) were carried out on a Perkin-

Elmer 240C analyser. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Jasco FT-IR 5300 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Jeol FX 90Q spectrometer (90 MHz, at 25°) using TMS as an internal standard. The purity of compounds was checked by tlc (silica gel G). *N*-Methylantranilic acid and ammonium *N*-aryldithiocarbamates were prepared by known methods⁴.

1-Methyl-3-phenyl-2-thio-2,4-(1H,3H)-quinazolidione (3a): A mixture of ammonium phenyl dithiocarbamate (3.72 g, 0.02 mol) and *N*-methylantranilic acid (3.02 g, 0.02 mol) in absolute ethanol (30 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath for 4.5 h, then cooled. The resulting solid was crystallised from benzene-ethanol as white crystals (68%), m.p. 298–300° (lit.⁵ 302–03°); ν_{\max} 1691 (C=O), 1380, 1221 (C=S) cm⁻¹; δ 3.96 (3H, s, N-CH₃), 7.01–8.09 (9H, m, ArH). Similarly, other compounds (3b-f) were prepared (yields 55–65%): 3b, m.p. 261–62°, δ 2.43 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.97 (3H, s, N-CH₃), 7.0–7.9 (8H, m, ArH); c, 230–31°, δ 3.97 (3H, s, N-CH₃), 7.0–7.91 (8H, m, ArH); d, 259–60°, δ 2.44 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.99 (3H, s, N-CH₃), 7.02–8.10 (7H, m, ArH); e, 235–37°, δ 3.70 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.98 (3H, s, N-CH₃), 7.02–7.98 (8H, m, ArH); f, 125–26°.

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